

EFFECT OF TEACCH METHOD IN DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT PRE-VOCATIONAL SKILLS OF PERSONS WITH AUTISM

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Abstract

The paper aims to study the effect of TEACCH method in the development of independence in pre-vocational skills of persons with autism in the areas of Kitchen skills, Office skills and Art and Craft skills. The TEACCH (Treatment and Education of Autistic and related Communication-handicapped Children) is an evidence based program that provides structured environments to enable learning in persons with autism. The study was undertaken using pre-intervention/post intervention experimental research design. A sample of 15 young adults with autism was selected using purposive sampling technique. A pre-intervention score was recorded on each individual where their readiness in each area was recorded. 10 intervention sessions were done. The level of support required by each individual was recorded during every session. The pre-intervention and post intervention level of support was recorded and compared to see the effect. The change in the level of support signified the achievement of independent working skills of these young adults. The program was done by special educators who have been trained on the use of the TEACCH program. The results obtained were quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed. Recording of pre-intervention and post-intervention scores was done by the level of accomplishment of task by the person in completing the task independently. Scoring pattern: Independent – 100, Verbal – 75, Gestural – 50, Physical support – 25. The pre-test scores revealed that the persons knew the tasks but were prompt dependent and they scored between 25 to 50. After providing intervention, scores of every individual moved up to 75 to 100. Mean scores, Df, t-values and significance of skill acquisition in each area was calculated. Many of them, post

intervention were able to complete the tasks independently without any support. Hence this indicates positive results in development of independent working skills through the TEACCH method in young adults with autism.

Keywords: TEACCH, Autism, Pre-vocational skills.

Introduction

Education is an important aspect for development of a human being. It improves productivity, creativity and promotes entrepreneurship and technological advances in people. Hence the main objective of education is to help people become responsible, independent, and contributing members of society. For young adults with special needs, the role of education is equally important so that their potential can be tapped and maximized which will enable them to lead productive lives.

Autism is a developmental disorder that typically appears during the first three years of life. It is a neurological disorder that affects the normal functioning of the brain, and affects development in the areas of social interaction and communication skills. People with autism display difficulties in social interaction, ability to communicate ideas and feelings, imagination, and establishment of relationships with others (National Research Council, 2002). Education for children with autism, provides opportunities for acquiring knowledge and abilities that enhance personal independence and socially responsible behaviour. Hence, educational goals for young adults with autism, must have emphasis on independent functioning productive behaviours.

Research studies show that children with autism respond well to structured educational program tailored to their specific needs. The severe challenges that some of them face is best addressed by an educational program that follows the behavioural approach, and is implemented in one to one or small group sessions (Vismara & Rogers, 2007; Lal & Lobo, 2007). Tasks that are given to them, if provided in a structured manner, with suitable visual supports, are better understood, enjoyable and easy for them to complete. Structure in teaching, and in the environment enables persons with autism to understand what is expected of them, encourages self control and enhances independent skills. Structured teaching approaches provide familiar, predictable and structured environments that reduce anxiety, promote independence, increase flexibility and tolerance for change (Quill, 2000, as cited in Simpson & Smith Myles, 2008).

TEACCH (Treatment and Education of Autistic and related Communication handicapped Children) is a program designed to provide the structure and predictability that children

with autism require to function successfully. This paper presents the findings of a research study conducted in Mumbai, India, to determine the effect of TEACCH based intervention on development of independent work skills in young adults with autism.

The TEACCH method:

The TEACCH program emphasizes on structured teaching. There are 4 elements of structured teaching which are as below:

- **Physical Structure:** This refers to the layout or surroundings of the student's environment, such as classroom, play room, home etc. The use of consistent, visually clear areas and boundaries for specific activities enables children with autism to better understand their environments and relationships between events. As children learn to function more independently, the physical structure can be gradually lessened.
- **Schedules:** They are visual cues that tell the students the sequence of activities that would occur during the day. Visual schedules help persons with autism in improving the sequential memory, receptive language, and attention problems.
- **Work Systems:** Work systems are essential for teaching independent work behavior. The system helps the student understand the work that is to be done; how much work to be done; indication of when the work is completed, and what happens after a given task is done. The work system facilitates independent work behavior.
- **Visual structure:** Visual structure refers to visual organization, clarification and instruction pertaining to tasks. When a task is presented in clear visual form it is easier for the children to identify its features. Since visual information is concrete and less dynamic, children learn the task easily.

The TEACCH method is broadly based on the principles of applied behavioural analysis. It recommends breaking the learning task into small steps that must be taught with prompts and the learning behaviour to be shaped with use of reinforcers

- **Instructions:** They consist of directions given to a child regarding the task that has to be done. Instructions may be verbal or nonverbal. The mode of instruction is selected to suit the functional level of the child.
- **Prompts:** A teacher uses prompts to shape a child's behaviour to the desired level. Prompts help a student to complete a new task. Different types of prompts may be used. Physical prompts are used to give manual assistance in task completion; verbal prompts are reminders for a task; gestural prompts

are signs or actions that point to or demonstrate the task; and visual prompts may use pictures/symbols/colour cards to cue the student to the task. Prompts should be used systematically. They must be offered before the student responds incorrectly.

- **Reinforcement:** Behaviours that are reinforced positively are likely to be repeated. Unlike neurotypical children, children with autism might be motivated by different items and activities which should be identified by the teacher and then presented to the student when a positive behaviour is demonstrated.

Aim of the study: To determine if training of young adults on the TEACCH system has an impact on the development of their independence in accomplishment of pre-vocational skills

Objectives: The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To study the effect of TEACCH system on the development of independent pre-vocational kitchen skills of young adults with autism
2. To study the effect of TEACCH system on the development of independent pre-vocational office skills of young adults with autism
3. To study the effect of TEACCH system on the development of independent pre-vocational art and craft skills of young adults with autism
4. To study the increment in skill development of young adults with autism when provided training on the TEACCH system
5. To compare the results of the increment in skill development across three skills taught to young adults with autism on the TEACCH system

Method: The TEACCH (Treatment and Education of Autistic and related Communication-handicapped Children) is an evidence-based program that provides structured environments to enable learning in persons with autism. The study was undertaken using pre-intervention/post intervention experimental research design. A pre-intervention score was recorded on each individual to identify their readiness in each area. 10 intervention sessions were done. The level of support required by each individual was recorded during every session. The pre-intervention and post intervention level of support was recorded and compared to see the effect. The change in the level of support signified the achievement of independent working skills of these young adults. Mean scores and differentiation of the scores were calculated. The degree of freedom (Df), t-value and the significance in each skill area was calculated.

Subjects: A sample of 15 young adults with autism between the ages of 12 and 16 were selected using purposive sampling technique. Diagnosis of autism was ascertained by their case file reports at the school they were attending.

Procedure: The intervention began after the students were pre tested on their functioning level on the 3 activities undertaken. The level was recorded as the prompt level they needed to do the task ((independent, verbal, gestural or physical). After 10 sessions of intervention on each task provided through TEACCH work system, the functioning levels were recorded. A typical intervention session proceeded in the following manner:

- Work table was prepared in advance with only task material set on the table. The work table contained sections where the task could be broken into small steps and visual pictures/symbols that denoted the activity, were put on the work system e.g. kitchen skills had a picture of unshelled peas in the first section labelled “Start”, a picture of a person shelling peas in the second and the third section labelled as “finish” section had the shelled peas picture
- Teacher sat next to the student and gave instructions on the activity, e.g. ‘shell peas’
- The student was prompted (independent, verbal, gestural or physical) to comply with the instruction.
- Rewards were presented after the student had reached ‘finished’ symbol

Skills taught to the students were as follows:

Kitchen skills: shelling peas

Office skills: stapling paper

Art and Craft skills: Making a Rakhi

Office skills

Kitchen skills

Art and craft skills

Results: The study aimed to determine the effect of TEACCH intervention on independent work behaviour of 15 students with autism. At the end of intervention period the change in the student's ability to understand and perform selected tasks independently was observed. The table below depicts the scores of each student in each task.

Pre-intervention and post-intervention scores

The pre-intervention and post-intervention scores reveal the following:

1. There is a significant improvement in the performance of the students post training on the TEACCH system in various skill areas
2. There is a significant difference in the scores across all students and across different skills.

Kitchen skills

Table 1.1

	Mean Scores	Diff in Mean scores	N	Df	t-value	Significance
Pre-Int	36.67	51.66	15	14	17.49	p<0.05
Post-Int	88.33		15			

3. The difference in mean scores is 51.66 and the t-value obtained is 17.49, ($p < 0.05$). Hence the improvement in the students after intervention is significant. It was observed that the students enjoyed this activity as many of them got a liked the sensation of handling the peas due to their tactile sensitivity

Office skills

Table 1.2

	Mean Scores	Diff in Mean scores	N	Df	t-value	Significance
Pre-Int	36.67	56.66	15	14	19.18	p<0.05
Post-Int	93.33		15			

4. The difference in mean scores is 56.66 and the t-value obtained is 19.18, ($p < 0.05$). The change post intervention is the highest in this skill. It was observed that this activity was easy for the students as the activity was repetitive and easy to comprehend.

Art and Craft skills

Table 1.3

	Mean Scores	Diff in Mean scores	N	Df	t-value	Significance
Pre-Int	31.67	51.66	15	14	13.48	$P < 0.05$
Post-Int	83.33		15			

5. The difference in mean scores was 51.67 and the t-value obtained is 13.48, ($p < 0.05$). The students learnt the task well. This activity required handling fevicol or the glue gun which all students were not entirely comfortable. But skill acquisition is seen in all the students.

Discussion: Educational strategies that provide structure and predictability to the learning process, allow children with autism to anticipate task requirements and set expectations, and teach a variety of skills across content areas in the natural environment. (Earles-Vollrath, et al. 2008). The TEACCH work system provides the structure and predictability which persons with autism require to develop independent functioning skills. In addition to the work system, teaching the task by breaking it down into small tasks and sequentially palcing the steps in a clear easy to understand work system helped the students achieve mastery over the skill sets. It is important to use this system early in

life with children with autism so that independent functioning comes early and the motivation to complete tasks develops.

Conclusion: Building on strengths and interests, rather than emphasizing on deficits is an important aspect of teaching. This is particularly true with persons with autism. The TEACCH method, respects the “culture of autism” as it provides structure and predictability which helps persons with autism achieve independent functioning. Drawing on children’s interests, however peculiar they may appear to most people, helps increase their understanding and motivation for tasks (Mesibov & Shea, 2003). The results of this study support the fact that TEACCH based intervention was effective in enhancing independent work behaviour in young adults with autism. The results of this research may be useful for people seeking appropriate intervention for persons with autism.

References

- Earles-Vollrath, T. C.-A. (2008). Instructional strategies to facilitate successful learning outcomes with children with autism. *Educating children and youth with autism: Strategies for effective practice*, 93-178.
- Hume, K. L. (2009). Increasing independence in autism spectrum disorders: A review of three focussed interventions. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders* , 39(9).
- Hungelmann, A. M. (Retrieved Jan. 2011.). An Analysis of TEACCH based home programming for young children with autism. . Available from <http://sitemaker.umich.edu/365.bernstein/teacch>.
- Lal, R. (2005). Effect of inclusive education on language and social development of children with autism. *Asia Pacific Disability Rehabilitation Journal*. 16.
- Lal, R. a. (2007). Discrete trial training and development of pre learning skills in intellectually impaired children with autism. *Journal of Rehabilitation Council of India*, 15-23.
- Mesibov, G. S. (2004). *The TEACCH Approach to Autism Spectrum Disorders*. New York: Springer, ISBN 978-0-306-48646-3.
- R., L. (2010). Effect of alternative and augmentative communication on language and social behaviour of children with autism. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 119-125.
- S, B.-C. (2002). *Trends in Cognitive Science*. Autism Society of India, 248-254.